

THE ROLE OF BUKHARA AND KHIVA KHANATES IN THE FORMATION OF FOREIGN RELATIONS OF THE KOKAND KHANATE: BASED ON A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

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Abstract. *The role of Bukhara and Khiva, two existing khanates in Central Asia in the Foreign Relations of the Kokand Khanate, was very important in history. Of course, each Khanate tried to expand its sphere of influence in the international arena to the extent possible. Including the Khanate of Kokand. In this article, the role of Bukhara and Khiva in the foreign policy of the Kokand Khanate was studied on the basis of a comparative analysis.*

Keywords: *Kokand Khanate, Bukhara Khanate, Khiva Khanate, Kokand question, foreign policy.*

РОЛЬ БУХАРСКОГО И ХИВИНСКОГО ХАНСТВ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ВНЕШНИХ СВЯЗЕЙ КОКАНДСКОГО ХАНСТВА: НА ОСНОВЕ СРАВНИТЕЛЬНОГО АНАЛИЗА

Аннотация. *Роль Бухары и Хивы, двух существовавших ханств в Средней Азии, во внешних связях Кокандского ханства была очень важной в истории. Конечно, каждое ханство старалось расширить сферу своего влияния на международной арене по мере возможности. В том числе и Кокандское ханство. В данной статье на основе сравнительного анализа изучена роль Бухары и Хивы во внешней политике Кокандского ханства.*

Ключевые слова: *Кокандское ханство, Бухарское ханство, Хивинское ханство, Кокандский вопрос, внешняя политика.*

As an active participant in the political, socio-economic processes in the Central Asian region, from the time of its creation, the Uzbek khanates had intense relations with neighboring countries. There were generally accepted conditions for such contacts, which, although some of them were not officially recorded during the period of its formation, but had to be strictly followed. In particular, one of the important provisions of neighborhood relations was the speedy delivery of the "exchange of power" issue to the governors of the surrounding province and the rulers of the neighboring state. The order charged the whistleblower with conveying the news of two events at the same time, either the cause of the death of the deceased Khan or his departure from power for certain reasons, and the accession of the new ruler.

In general, the tradition of informing each other about the changes that have occurred within the country in the khanates of Central Asia is very well established. Of course, this rule was also necessary to justify the official status of the country, that is, the right to conduct official relations with other states as an equal and independent subject of international relations.

In the formation of Foreign Relations of the Kokand Khanate, there were influences from various aspects of the Bukhara and Khiva khanates, which, on the one hand, were associated with political processes in the Khanate, and on the other, with economic relations. At this point, the researcher N.Allayeva believes that in the relations between Bukhara and Khiva, the “*Kokand question*” had also arisen [1:183]

At this time, the Khan of Kokand, Amir Umarchan, was striving to promote socio-economic and cultural development and independently conduct foreign policy, ensuring internal stability in the Khanate. In exchange for this behavior, Khan begins to compete for control of the “plundering” territories, which are also causing discussion, completely getting rid of the influence of the neighboring emirate of Bukhara. In particular, information about this is also confirmed by information from the work “history of Turkestan”. That is, during the Umarchan period, the state system of the Kokand Khanate, the laws and regulations for carrying out state affairs, religious affairs were regulated, and the borders of the country were determined. Now the border of the Kokand State reached as far as Turkestan and Dashti Kipchak in the north, as far as Samarkand in the West, as far south as Kohistan and Kolob, Hisor and Shahrissabz, and as far east as Turkestan.

Upon the death of umarchan on 30 December 1822, during the reign of his successor Muhammadalihan (1822-1842), the Government of Kokand is recognized by KO'ab, Hisor, Badakhshan, Darvoz, Maschoh. Under muhammadalihan, some districts of Kyrgyz were annexed to Kokand. But the O'ratepa region remained the site of battles and wars for Kokand and Bukhara.

Only the people suffered from these Wars [2:10].

While Amir Umar Khan focused the early periods of his reign on restoring his position in the country and ensuring the legitimacy (legitimation) of his power, the next aspiration was to define his status as the influential rulers of the Muslim world among the neighboring khanates of Bukhara and Khiva. Research scientists assess the processes involved as “Umarchan's move toward diplomatic legitimation” [3:150].

Amir Umar Khan of Kokand initially focused on improving relations with the Khanate of Khiva in establishing Foreign Relations. This is documented in Munis and Ogahi's “Firdavs ul-iqbol” as follows. “Syed Muhammad Haji came to Khiva Khan Muhammad Rahim I as ambassador to the Qooqan Khan Amir Umarchan” [4:414-415]. N.Allayeva, also relying on historical sources [1: 184], indeed informed the Khiva Khan Muhammad Rahim I Umarchan of his military campaigns into the territories of the Dashti Kipchak and Eastern Turkestan, wishing

him success in this March and even sending royal gifts and tributes, in a letter he would be an ally with the Kokand. Information about this is also preserved in archival documents [5:220-244], according to the analysis of researchers, the following information is recorded in letters on the interaction of the Khiva Khanate with the Khagan Khanate. That is, their content records correspondence between rulers, letters about the situation in Kokand by representatives of the Khiva Khanate, letters of the Kokand living in the Khiva Khanate asking for material assistance from the Khiva Khan, the duties of ambassadors in relations between the Khiva and the Khanate of Kokand [6:49].

Also, Mirzo Qalandar Mushrif Khiva Khan, author of "Shohnomai Nusratpayom", writes in a letter to the Qooqan Khan of Muhammad Rahim I that he saw the rulers of Bukhara as their common enemy [7:132]. It can be seen from this that the Kokand Khanate relied more on the Khanate of Khiva in establishing and strengthening external relations. From the content of the work, the Khan of Kokand Amir Umarchan did not reject this proposal of Khiva Khan. Even in response to the proposal, ambassador Abdukholik sends his guard to Khiva.

Amir Nasrullo also made the most of the political depression in the Kokand Khanate. Mirzo scholar Mahdum Haji in his "history of Turkestan" wrote that the emir with his troops occupied the city of Kokand in the spring of 1842 and stayed in Kokand for 13 days, then many artisan Cossacks in the Khanate forcibly took the Masters to Bukhara. Many women also leave their homeland and face pride and strangeness. Amir Nasrullah Ibrahim parvonachi manghit is khakim in Kokand and returns to Bukhara himself. Ibrahim parvonachi's "betrayal" would impose new taxes during the two-month reign, inflicting great havoc on the Fergana people.

After 70 days, the Kokand people, with the forces of the Kipchak and Kyrgyz communities, drive the mangit from Kokand and raise Sheralikhan to the throne. The success of the New Khan will also be fueled by Khiva Khan's attack on the Emirate of Bukhara. Shortly thereafter, the Kokand Khanate would regain its previous borders. Voles began to be reassigned to properties from Kokand to Tashkent, Khojand and southern Kazakhstan" [2:11], "leaving information.

The Kokand scholar. In his podcast to uzanalytics, Vohidov notes interesting historical information about the relations of the Kokand Khanate with the inhabitants of the neighboring Kazakh steppe. Specifically, it states that "... The Kokand Khan Olimkhan, who occupied Tashkent in 1804-1806, sent troops to South Kazakhstan – modern South Kazakhstan. We know that during the reign of umarkhan, the south of Kazakhstan was conquered, and the fortifications of the Kokand Khanate were built along the shores of Syrdarya. These fortifications horrified the Kazakh ovules, since the way of life of the local Kokand was radically different from the nomadic way of life of the Kazakhs, but the Kazakhs themselves always plundered Bukharan, Caucasian and Khiva merchants. The reason is known to yourself: there was one of the ways to make a fortune.

Borimta (pulling his cattle because he offended the Turkic nomadic peoples, or providing mutilation for the damage done) was a group of Kazakh tribal men who organized to capture and rob caravans" [8]. From these expressed opinions, Amir Umarchan was able to dare to expand the territory of his country's border to the Northeast without worrying about the emirate of Bukhara after the "confidence" expressed by the Khanate of Khiva.

A special place in the development of the Bukhara Khanate, which was formed in the second half of the 16th century and occupied a special place in Central Asia until the beginning of the 20th century, is also occupied by its foreign relations with other states. If the features of the Kokand Khanate in its external relations are comparative analysis with the Bukharan Khanate, we observe that both khanates are equally interested in External Relations. Researcher A. Berdiyev's monograph analyzed the data as follows. In particular, Abdullah Khan II, who founded a large centralized state, is reported to have tried to promote relations with other khanates and states in order to ensure the security of the country, to promote trade, with particular emphasis on the relations that would be with countries that were territorial neighbors and located along the Great Silk Road. It is also noted that the ranks of such states included many states such as India, Iran, Russia, Astrakhan, Kazan khanates, Yorkend and Qoshgar khanates, Kazakh Khanate, Khiva Khanate, Ottoman Empire. In its place, it is also remembered that the above countries from the second half of the 16th century tried to maintain friendly relations with the Bukhara Khanate, which had a military and politically powerful power in Central Asia, in addition, they were interested in the development of Foreign Relations due to mutual trade [9:7-10]. Favorable and unfavorable geographical conditions can also be considered sufficient for the establishment of Foreign Relations of the Kokand Khanate. Russian tourists and traders can also learn from travelogues that when they become ambassadors to the Khanate of Kokand here they record their sight on the merchants and ambassadors from Bukhara, Khiva and Iran. In particular, Philip Nazarov, translator of the Sibir Corps, records in his work that in the details of his 1813 trip to the Kokand Khanate, the Kokand established heated trade relations with countries such as Koshgar, Khiva, Bukhara, China [10:125]. As can be seen from this, political goals such as strengthening foreign relations were also pursued, as well as establishing the Khanate's mutual trade relations with neighboring Bukhara and Khiva.

Among the rulers who ruled the Kokand Khanate, especially Olimkhan, during the reign of Umarchan, significant changes in the direction of the Khanate's foreign policy were observed.

This line aimed to establish relations with the major political powers of the time and with the states of political power. One such country is the Ottoman Turkish state. The Ottomans, known as the "state Supreme", had political power in their day.

Umarkhan's vision from his ambassadorial contacts was his concern at the establishment of Russian fortress fortifications on the northern borders of the Khanate. So, salkam predicted that 20 years ago, Umarkhon would invade the khanates of Russia. Therefore, Umarkhan improved relations with the neighboring Khanate of Khiva. By the 18th – 19th centuries, the prestige of the Kokand Khanate was growing not only in Central Asia, but throughout the Muslim world. In such circumstances, the rulers of the Kokand Khanate place great emphasis on their foreign diplomatic relations from a security point of view in order to preserve their prestige.

In particular, the aim of establishing and strengthening diplomatic relations with the Ottoman Turks was to establish relations both politically and economically. From such contacts it was the fact that the Ottoman Turks also had interests that the Turkish sultan Mahmut 2 handed over the Khans label to the Kokand Khan Umarkhan. It was a major label at the time and was introduced to the lone Kokand Khanate in Central Asia.

Generally in the early 19th century, the Khanate of Kokand established heated relations with neighboring states, sending its envoys to these states as well. Historical sources have preserved information about the ambassadors of the Caucasus to the Emirate of Bukhara, the Khanate of Khiva, Eastern Turkestan and China.

In place of the conclusion, it can be said that the External Relations of the Kokand Khanate were formed in extremely complex conditions. Political tensions, especially between the Uzbek khanates, were a deterrent.

REFERENCES

1. Аллаева Н.А. Хива хонлигининг дипломатияси ва савдо алоқалари. Тошкент: “Akademnashr”, 2019. – 361 б.
2. Мирзо Олим Махмуд хожи «Тарихи Туркистон». – Тошкент: «Янги аср авлоди», 2008. – 246 б.
3. Бабаджанов Б.М. Кокандское ханство: власть, политика, религия. Токио-Ташкент: Институт востоковедения АНРУз, 2010. – 744 с.
4. Мунис ва Огаҳий. Фирдавс ул-икбол (Араб ёзувидан табдил этган, кириш ва изоҳлар муаллифи: Шодмон Воҳидов, Исмоил Бекчанов, Неъматжон Полвонов). – Т.: Янги аср авлоди, 2010. – 520 б.
5. Ўзбекистон Миллий архиви. Хива хонлиги девонхонаси хужжатлари, И-125-фонд, 2-рўйхат, 220-244 йиғмажилдлар.
6. Ахмедова Д. Мактублар манба сифатида//Ўтмишга назар. – Т.: 2023. №SI-1. – Б. 49.
7. Мирзо Қаландар Мушриф Исфарагий. Шохномаи Умархоний // Қўлёзма ТФАШИ. – № 10088. – 132 б.

8. Кокандской ханства. 2023 йил 22 март. <https://www.Uzanalytics.com /tarix /10617/>
9. Бердиев А. XVIII–XIX асрларда Ўрта Осиё хонликларининг ташқи дипломатик алоқалари тарихи. Монография. – Тошкент.: Ўз.китоб нашриёти. – Б. 7–10.
10. Филипп Назаров. Записки о некоторых народах и землях средней части Азии. - М.: Наука. 1968. – С. 125.
11. ЎзР МА. 715-фонд, 1-р., 29-йиғма жилд. 172-варак.
12. Тўраев Ш. Ўрта аср Европа сайёҳлари асарларида Ўрта Осиё - Тарихи ва маданиятининг ёритилиши. Тарих фан.бўйича фалсафа док.дисс. Қарши. 2021. – Б. 113.
13. Турсунов Б. Исследование истории Кокандского ханства в советскую эпоху. DOI 10.24412/2413-2004-2022-1-22-30. – С. 24.
14. Васильев Д. Знамя и мечь от падишаха. – М.: 2014. – С. 187.
15. Исҳоқхон Тўра Ибрат. Тарихи Фарғона. – Тошкент.: “Маънавият”, 2005. – Б. 17.